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INTER COMPONENT PHASE PROCESSING OF SPEECH SIGNALS
FOR THEIR RECOGNITION AND IDENTIFICATION OF ANNOUNCERS

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The characteristics of the phase differences between quasi harmonic components of speech signals is proposed to use for the solution of speech recognition task and identification of the announcers. The simplest procedure of speech signals inter component phase processing is realized for harmonic on frequency of the basic tone and overtones with approximately divisible by its frequencies. The estimation of a phase difference between frequency components of analyzed signal can be distributed on formants as well using the coordinated moving of selective windows with multiple central frequencies or their rational attitude along a spectrum of a signal. The inter component phase processing is applicable not only for speech, but also for many other kinds of superbroadband and polyharmonic signals.

Introduction. In XIX century George Ohm, more known under the law, established by him, in the field of an electricity, for the first time has noted the fact of perception by the man's ear the simultaneously acting harmonic acoustic fluctuations as a chord, instead of as one complex sound. «Conformity, that we hear, and representation of sounds as separate components, became known as the Ohms law» [1]. Since then in speech signals (SS) the spectral components are traditionally considered mainly outside of connection with each other.

The numerous experiences have shown that the shifts of phases between harmonic components of SS do not *directly* influence on their acoustical perception [2]. However, this is not followed by fact that these parameters get every time any meanings and are obviously non informative.

Refs. [3-7] shown that the analysis of phase differences of multi frequencies components and components with the rational attitudes of frequencies is one of the perspective kinds for revealing of specific inter component connections in superbroadband and polyharmonic radio and hydro location signals, and also acoustic speech signals. The conclusions on expediency of its use for the decision of detection, recognition and diagnostics of signal sources task are made.

Probable expediency of the account of SS narrow-band components initial phases was specified in [9,10]. However, data on issues of inter component phase processing of SS in the known publications do not contain.

The materials indicating informative estimations of phase differences between fluctuation with frequency of the basic tone (BT) and overtones of vowel sounds are given below.

The mathematical analysis. Selecting only fluctuation of BT and overtones, the realization of a processed vowel sound $x(t)$ can be given as

$$x_k(t) = \sum_{p=1}^{p=N} A_{kp}(t) \cos(2\pi F_{k0} p t + \Phi_{kp}(t)), \quad k = \overline{1, M}, \quad (1)$$

where $A_{kp}(t)$ and $\Phi_{kp}(t)$ - slowly varying amplitude and phase of p quasi harmonic component for k realization of a sound $x(t)$; F_{k0} - BT in k realization; M - amount of realizations; N - number of chosen for the analysis quasi harmonic components.

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In the formula (1) arguments cosine are represented by (with) the current meaning (importance) of a complete phase p quasiharmonics of fluctuation in k of realization of a sound $x(t)$, equal

$$\Psi_{kp}(t) = 2\pi F_{k0} p t + \Phi_{kp}(t); \quad p = \overline{1, N}; \quad (k = \overline{1, M}) \quad (2)$$

If $\Psi_{kp}(t)$ divides on p and result is subtracted from a complete phase $\Psi_{k1}(t)$ of fluctuations with BT ($p = 1$), the certain difference of phases $\Delta\Psi_{k1}^p(t)$ between fluctuation with BT and p quasi harmonic component does not contain linearly increasing items:

$$\Delta\Psi_{k1}^p(t) = \Phi_{k1}(t) - \Phi_{kp}(t)/p, \quad p = \overline{1, N}; \quad k = \overline{1, M} \quad (3)$$

Note that for mutual destruction of the mentioned components in the formula (3) it is required to ensure a continuity of functions $\Phi_{k1}(t)$ and $\Phi_{kp}(t)$, that is achieved by application of known procedure for their "lacing" in points of quasi periodical phase jumps on value of 2π .

One can be convinced that a range of unique definition of value $\Delta\Psi_{k1}^p(t)$ is interval $[0; 2\pi/p]$. Therefore, values $\Delta\Psi_{k1}^p(t)$ calculated according to the formula (3) should be normalized on the module $|2\pi/p|$:

$$\Delta\Psi_{k1}^p(t) = \left[\Phi_{k1}(t) - \Phi_{kp}(t)/p \right] \left| \frac{2\pi}{p} \right., \quad p = \overline{1, N}; \quad k = \overline{1, M} \quad (4)$$

Generally, for the case of analysis of phase difference between any of q and p quasi harmonic components, formula (4) will be presented as

$$\Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t) = \left[\Phi_{kp}(t) - \Phi_{kq}(t) p/q \right] \left| \frac{2\pi p}{q} \right., \quad p = \overline{1, N}; \quad q = \overline{2, N}; \quad k = \overline{1, M} \quad (5)$$

Complete phases $\Psi_{kp}(t)$ of filtered and separately accessible to transformations quasi harmonic components $A_{kp}(t) \cos(\Psi_{kp}(t))$, $p = \overline{1, N}$; $k = \overline{1, M}$ can be defined using transition to *analytical* signals by Hilbert's transformation.

For the phase characteristic of different speech sounds of various announcers in the decision of tasks of recognition and identification generally a vector can be used:

$\{ \Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t) \}$, $p = \overline{1, N}$, $q = \overline{2, M}$, that can be named as a *phase quasi invariant* (PQI).

Experimental details. The digital records of four announcers - men (A, D, S, V) SS were made in a laboratory having protection against acoustic noise and noise of vibrations with a level < 40 dB. Registration and analysis of SS were carried out with the help of the computer on the basis of the processor Pentium II. For input of SS a microphone such as M-101 and 16-digit sound adapter were used.

The sampling frequency was 22050 Гц. The applied programs package WaveLab 4.0d was used for temporary selection of sounds and words. Spectral, cepstral analysis and inter component phase processing of digital records were carried out using specially developed programs.

For example, we explain here the processing of fluctuations on BT and overtones with $p = (2,3,4)$. The features of estimation of a phases difference between overtones with $p = 2$ and $q = 4$ can be understood, comparing the formulas (4) and (5).

Each realization $x_k(t)$; $k = \overline{1, M}$ of a sound $x(t)$ was passed through equal to its duration Hanning's time window. From data of its spectral and cepstral analysis the estimations of average (on duration of a sound) value of BT F_{k0} were made.

The band-pass filtration of sound on BT and frequencies involved for the overtones analysis was carried out in bands (0,1-0,2) from the central frequencies. For the filtered quasi harmonic signals on BT and on frequency of p overtone their analytical representations were formed and phases and envelops were calculated using Hilbert transformation.

Then the time interval was determined when *joint* envelops of compared by phases oscillations exceed a level of 0,7. The phases of these oscillations were combined as functions of time in the jump discontinuity points (jumps on level 2π).

According to the formulas (4) or (5) the phase differences $\Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t)$ were calculated and the average value of $\Delta\Psi_p^q = \overline{\Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t)}$, $k = \overline{1, M}$ were defined. The angular brackets and top feature her symbolize calculations of average values of functions $\Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t)$ both on time and on ensemble of realizations.

Results and discussion. An example of intercomponent phase processing results on the basic tone and overtones for data received after analysis of a shock sound "A" in a word "DVA" is presented in Table 1.

A five realizations of SS with rather monotonous pronouncing (at hearing perception) of the mentioned words by the announcers A, D, S and V were used.

The table. Average meanings $\Delta\Psi_p^q$ ($p = 1, 2$; $q = 2, 3, 4$) of components phase quasi invariant $\{ \Delta\Psi_{kp}^q(t) \}$ for the announcers A, D, S, and V appreciated on a shock sound "A" records in a word "DVA" by averaging on duration of each realization and on ensemble of realizations (all in degrees).

The announcer	BT, Hz	$\Delta\Psi_1^2$	$\Delta\Psi_1^3$	$\Delta\Psi_1^4$	$\Delta\Psi_2^4$
A	151 - 168	95	95	30	51
D	201 - 206	49	104	12	92
S	171 - 204	40	107	23	121
V	195 - 214	50	105	17	114

Given example shown that the values of components PQI of the various announcers at pronouncing the same sound differs significantly. The similar situation generally takes place and for various sounds made by each announcer.

The conclusions.

1. The estimations of phase differences between quasi harmonic components of SS on BT and divisible frequencies appear a little bit varied on duration of tone sounds, generally various for different sounds, that are individual and steady for the different announcers.

2. The important feature of SS phase processing is its lowered sensitivity (at the absence of interference – a complete tolerance) to changes of analyzed SS intensity.

3. The offered above concept of phases quasi invariant (PQI) can be used for the characteristic of phase ratio between frequency components of various SS sounds of the various announcers. This characteristic of inter component phase ratio can be applied for both components with divisible central frequencies, and their rational ratios.

4. The estimation of phase difference between frequency components can be distributed on any spectrum regions including formants with the help of coordinated movement of selective windows with divisible central frequencies or their rational ratio along a spectrum of an analyzed signal. Inter component phase processing is applicable not only for speech, but also for many other kinds of super broadband and polyharmonic signals.

5. In cases, when traditionally used parameters of speech (such as BT, data of the formant analysis etc.) are insufficient for achievement of required detection quality of SS recognition and identification of the announcers the use of PQI estimations can give the necessary additional information.

6. The analysis of efficiency of quasi invariant phase estimations application for the processing of SS and others super broadband and polyharmonic signals requires accumulation of the statistically representative data.

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